

MISSION-DRIVEN LEADERSHIP: AN EMERGENT THEORY

John Mark N. Saldivar

College of Teacher Education, La Salle University- Ozamiz City, Misamis Occidental, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Private education significantly contributes to achieving the fourth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), with instructional leaders playing a pivotal role in shaping the vision and direction of schools. This study aimed to generate a theory on the leadership style among young private school heads. Using a deductive axiomatic approach in theory generation, the following axioms are generated: (1) Mission-driven leaders are aligned with the organization's core values; (2) Mission-driven leaders inspire and motivate; (3) Mission-driven leaders are strategically focused; and (4) Mission-driven leaders are adaptive to change. From these axioms, four propositions were derived: (A) Leaders who align with the organization's core values build cohesion and trust, increasing employee loyalty; (B) Leaders who effectively communicate the organization's mission and vision inspire and motivate employees, resulting in higher levels of engagement and productivity; (C) Leaders focused on mission-related goals drive accountability, performance excellence, and competitive advantage; (D) Leaders who exhibit adaptability and flexibility in response to changing environments and challenges foster organizational resilience and sustain competitive advantage. From these axioms and propositions, the Mission-Driven Leadership Theory was developed, which posited that a mission-driven leader is aligned with the organization's core values, inspires and motivates, is strategically focused, and is adaptive to change. The convergence of the two core attributes of Mission-Driven Leadership – Alignment and Focus, and Inspiration and Adaptability, creates a robust framework that fosters innovation, sustained success, and organizational cohesiveness.

Keywords: *mission-driven leadership, private school heads, deductive axiomatic approach, theory generation*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a powerful tool for breaking the cycle of poverty and inequality. High-quality education fosters sustainable development by empowering individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary for economic growth and innovation (World Bank, 2018). "Quality Education" is the fourth of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), emphasizing inclusive and equitable education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities. It aims to ensure that by 2030, all girls and boys complete accessible, equitable, and quality primary and secondary education (United Nations, 2023). The focus is not only on access but also on the quality of education, which includes effective learning outcomes and relevant skills for employment and entrepreneurship (UNESCO, 2020).

Meanwhile, private education is crucial in advancing the fourth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Private schools can help bridge gaps in public education systems, providing additional resources and innovative teaching methods that may not be available in public schools (UNESCO, 2019). They often have more flexibility to implement cutting-edge curricula and technology, fostering a more adaptable and skilled workforce for the future (OECD, 2020). In many developing countries, private education helps address the shortage of public education facilities, offering access to education where public infrastructure is lacking (World Bank, 2020). Private institutions also contribute to higher education, supporting research and development that can drive sustainable practices and innovations (United Nations, 2021).

However, there are concerns about equity, as private education can exacerbate social inequalities by being accessible primarily to wealthier families (UNESCO, 2021). Thus, partnerships between private educational institutions and governments can enhance the quality and reach of education, combining resources and expertise from both sectors (UNICEF, 2022). These collaborations can support teacher training, infrastructure development, and curriculum improvements, benefiting a broader range of students. Furthermore, private education providers can play a role in lifelong learning, offering programs that help adults reskill and adapt to changing job markets (International Labor Organization, 2019). Ensuring that private education aligns with the principles of inclusivity and equity is vital for achieving the SDGs. Regulatory frameworks and policies must be in place to oversee private institutions, ensuring they contribute positively to the broader educational ecosystem (UNESCO, 2020). Private education can significantly impact sustainable development, but careful management must ensure it complements and enhances public education efforts rather than undermines them.

As prime movers of the private education sector, the school heads sign image defiantly contribute to ensuring quality and accessible education as they set the vision and direction for their schools. As instructional leaders, they are responsible for creating a

positive and conducive learning environment that promotes academic excellence and holistic development (Leithwood et al., 2020). They develop and implement strategic plans aligning with educational standards and policies, ensuring all students receive a high-quality education. By fostering a culture of continuous improvement, school heads encourage teachers and staff to strive for excellence and innovation in their teaching practices. Their leadership drives school-wide initiatives that enhance student learning outcomes and overall performance. Effective school heads prioritize professional development for their teachers, recognizing that teacher quality is a significant factor in student achievement. They facilitate ongoing training and development opportunities that help educators stay current with the latest teaching methods and subject matter expertise (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). By supporting teachers' professional growth, school heads ensure that the instructional practices within their schools are both practical and innovative. Additionally, they provide mentorship and coaching to new and experienced teachers alike, helping them to refine their skills and improve their classroom practices. This focus on professional development creates a supportive and collaborative environment that benefits teachers and students.

Meanwhile, recent studies provide further insights into the leadership styles of private school heads in the Philippines. One relevant study by Yacon and Cayaban (2023) found that adaptive leadership is a crucial trait among private school heads, where leaders adjust their strategies based on the changing educational landscape and specific needs of their schools. This flexibility is essential for managing crises and ensuring the school's continuous improvement. During the COVID-19 pandemic, private school heads have confronted several noteworthy obstacles that have resulted in an educational shift. Among the main problems is the requirement for crisis management abilities that work. A thorough literature analysis reveals that school administrators had to quickly adjust to new circumstances throughout the pandemic, such as switching to online learning and handling disruptions in educational services (Chatzipanagiotou & Katsarou, 2023).

Moreover, private school heads often grapple with financial constraints. The economic impact of the pandemic led to reduced enrollment and financial instability, making it difficult for schools to maintain operations and pay staff. This financial strain also hampers their ability to invest in necessary technological infrastructure for effective online learning (Yacon & Cayaban, 2023).

Furthermore, a study by Jian (2022) highlights the importance of relational leadership, where school heads prioritize building solid relationships with their staff, students, and parents. It emphasizes building strong, supportive relationships with teachers, students, and parents. This leadership style fosters a collaborative and inclusive school environment, enhancing overall performance and student well-being. It involves effective communication, trust-building, and active stakeholder engagement to create a sense of community and shared responsibility (McKimm et al., 2023). Relational leaders prioritize their interactions' emotional and social aspects, ensuring that all school community members feel valued and heard (Santos et al., 2021). This approach not only improves morale and motivation among teachers but also leads to better student outcomes and a more positive school culture (Dizon, 2021).

Another study by Dizon (2021) emphasizes the role of participative leadership in private schools. This style involves engaging teachers and other stakeholders in decision-making, leading to more innovative and practical solutions to school challenges. Participative leadership, also called democratic leadership, highlights transformational and distributed leadership. Transformational leadership requires more support in handling uncertain situations and work-related stress among teachers (Ko, 2024; Yacon & Cayaban, 2023; Thomas, 2024). School leaders must enhance crisis management and leadership strategies to ensure a supportive work environment.

Additionally, private school heads often need help maintaining educational quality and standards. They must balance administrative duties with academic leadership, which can be overwhelming without adequate training and support systems (Acido & Kilongkilong, 2022). Additionally, the evolving academic landscape requires leaders well-versed in traditional and modern educational practices, including integrating technology into teaching and learning (Chatzipanagiotou & Katsarou, 2023; Ko, 2024). Distributed leadership, on the other hand, found that sharing leadership responsibilities among various school members enhances school innovation and effectiveness. This approach also promotes a sense of ownership and accountability among teachers and staff, leading to better school outcomes (Santos et al., 2021).

Private school administrators also play a dual responsibility as instructional leaders and administrators. According to Pandey et al. (2024), a school leader's ability to effectively lead education is essential to a school's success. The school's mission and goals must be clearly stated, a pleasant learning environment must be fostered, curriculum and instruction must be managed, and student achievement must be tracked. In addition to overseeing the institution, school administrators also serve as instructional leaders. The instructional leadership of the school leader determines the school's efficacy (Rashdi & Khamis, 2018). They further opined that private school heads generally have more autonomy and influence over vital school-level decisions than public school principals. They have greater authority in setting students' performance standards, developing the school curriculum, hiring and training teachers, establishing disciplinary policies, and managing institutional budgets.

Rodrigues and de Lima (2024) also posited that instructional leadership underscores that private school heads who focus on the core business of teaching and learning significantly boost student academic outcomes. By providing instructional guidance and support to teachers, these leaders ensure high education standards and continuous professional growth for their staff. Similarly, research by Vikaraman et al., (2021) and Ogbechie (2023) found that ethical leadership is critical in private schools, where leaders who model ethical behavior and decision-making build trust and integrity within the school community.

Finally, Andacao (2014) explored the impact of visionary leadership, where school heads with a clear and compelling vision drive their schools toward long-term success. These leaders inspire their school communities to embrace change and work towards common goals, resulting in improved school performance and student outcomes. Accordingly, inspirational leaders mold school learning environments by encouraging high standards,

creativity, and long-term progress (Day et al., 2016). Moreover, cooperative and adaptive facets of visionary leadership, emphasizing its function in utilizing technology and distributed methods for innovative teaching, were also given premium importance (Harris et al., 2021). Nonetheless, visionary leadership fosters equitable and socially just school environments, increases teacher motivation, and inspires positive school cultures (Hallinger & Heck, 2010)

While there are studies that link school heads' motivation and their leadership styles, this scarcity prompted the researcher to explore other knowledge gaps about the study's subject. One significant gap in research is the lack of studies that track motivation changes over time as these young leaders gain experience. Understanding how motivations evolve can provide insights into leadership development and retention (Leithwood et al., 2020). Additionally, more research is needed on how generational differences impact motivations. Young school heads, often Millennials or Generation Z, may have different values and priorities than their older counterparts, yet this needs to be thoroughly explored in current literature. Other research limitations include the insufficient focus on young school heads' intrinsic versus extrinsic motivations (Ryan & Deci, 2000) and the role of personal background, such as socioeconomic status, education, and family influences, in shaping their motivations. These professional development opportunities impact their motivation and career satisfaction (Rhodes & Brundrett, 2009), the impact of organizational culture and support systems (Day et al., 2011), and the effects of policy changes and societal expectations (Gurr, 2014).

Research Questions

This study sought to generate a theory on young private school heads' characteristics and leadership styles and comprehensively establish empirical evidence supporting the theoretical framework. Specifically, this theory generation aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What theory can be generated based on axioms and propositions?
2. What recommendations for future theory validation can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized the axiomatic deductive approach in theory development. The axiomatic deductive approach involves establishing a set of axioms or fundamental principles from which conclusions are logically derived. This method is particularly useful in developing and testing theories where clear, logical deductions can validate or invalidate hypotheses (Johnson & Christensen, 2020). By adhering to logical rules, the researcher ensured that the conclusions were logically consistent and built upon established principles in the social sciences. This method aims to create a structured framework where each step in the reasoning process is transparent and verifiable, ensuring the validity and coherence of the conclusions drawn.

Axioms are foundational principles or assumptions that provide the starting point for logical deductions in various fields. According to Babbie (2020), hypotheses are fundamental truths or accepted premises essential for constructing theoretical frameworks in social research. These hypotheses are crucial because they establish the basic premises from which propositions are derived through deductive reasoning. Moreover, in educational contexts, as explored by LeCompte and Schensul (2021), axioms are fundamental to developing theoretical frameworks that guide research methodologies and data analysis procedures. They provide a solid foundation for constructing and testing hypotheses using empirical data.

On the other hand, propositions, as discussed by Johnson and Christensen (2020), are statements that logically follow from axioms and serve as hypotheses or predictions that researchers aim to validate or invalidate through empirical investigation. This deductive approach ensures that each proposition is rigorously derived from the axioms, maintaining logical coherence and validity in scientific inquiry. This study's formulation of the Mission-Driven Leadership theory is based on the deductive axiomatic approach illustrated by the five steps in theory development (Padua, 2012)

Figure 1. Deductive Axiomatic Approach in Theory Development (Padua, 2012)

RESULTS

Understanding the pattern of motivation among young private school heads involves exploring various factors that drive their professional aspirations and behaviors within educational leadership contexts. Private school heads play a crucial role in ensuring the acquisition of quality education by students through their leadership and administrative decisions. They oversee the implementation of educational standards, curriculum development, and teaching methodologies that promote academic excellence and student achievement. By fostering a supportive learning environment and maintaining high standards of teaching and learning, private school heads contribute to the holistic development of students. Their leadership also influences teachers' professional growth and morale, enhancing instructional practices and student outcomes. Ultimately, their commitment to educational quality helps cultivate a competitive advantage and positive reputation for the school within the community and among stakeholders.

After due deliberation and careful analysis and synthesis from the related studies, the researcher was able to draw out fundamentally relevant and universally accurate statements that would form the basis of the theoretical framework of the study. The following axioms include: (1) Mission-driven leaders are aligned with the organization's core values; (2) Mission-driven leaders inspire and motivate; (3) Mission-driven leaders are strategically focused; and (4) Mission-driven leaders are adaptive to change. From the five axioms formulated, the following propositions were derived: (A) Leaders who align with the organization's core values build cohesion and trust, increasing employee loyalty; (B) Leaders who effectively communicate the organization's mission and vision inspire and motivate employees, resulting in higher levels of engagement and productivity; (C) Leaders focused on mission-related goals drive accountability, performance excellence, and competitive advantage; (D) Leaders who exhibit adaptability and flexibility in response to changing environments and challenges foster organizational resilience and sustain competitive advantage.

Table 1 presents the axioms and propositions created.

Axioms	Propositions
1. Mission-driven leaders are aligned with the organization's core values.	1. Leaders who align with the organization's core values build cohesion and trust, increasing employee loyalty.
2. Mission-driven leaders inspire and motivate.	2. Leaders who effectively communicate the organization's mission and vision inspire and motivate employees, resulting in higher engagement and productivity.
3. Mission-driven leaders are strategically focused.	3. Leaders focused on mission-related goals drive accountability, performance excellence, and competitive advantage.

4. Mission-driven leaders are adaptive to change.

4. Leaders who exhibit adaptability and flexibility in response to changing environments and challenges foster organizational resilience and sustain competitive advantage

DISCUSSION

Axiom 1: Mission-driven leaders are aligned with the organization's core values.

Mission-driven leaders align their strategic choices and operations with the organization's core purpose, fostering a unified work environment. This alignment boosts morale, productivity, and stakeholder trust (George, 2022). Strategic decision-making prioritizes long-term goals, cultivating a culture of accountability and ethical behavior. This alignment attracts and retains employees with similar values, attracting a more committed workforce. Mission-driven leaders can enhance an organization's reputation and navigate challenges effectively. Aligning decisions with the mission and core values is crucial for sustainable success and resilience in the ever-changing business landscape (Brown & Treviño, 2020).

Proposition 1: Leaders who align with the organization's core values build cohesion and trust, increasing employee loyalty.

Mission-driven leaders consistently prioritize the organization's mission and values in decision-making. By doing so, they create a cohesive and purpose-driven environment where every action and decision is guided by the overarching goals and principles of the organization (Axiom 1). This alignment ensures that employees perceive a unified direction and purpose, strengthening their commitment to the organization's mission. When leaders align decisions with the mission, they signal to employees that their actions are strategic, meaningful, and supportive of the organization's long-term objectives. This clarity fosters a sense of trust and transparency, as employees understand the rationale behind leadership decisions and see how their work contributes to the broader mission. As a result, employees are more likely to feel engaged with their work, as they see a direct connection between their efforts and the organization's success.

Axiom 2: Mission-driven leaders inspire and motivate.

Mission-driven leaders inspire and motivate by clearly communicating the organization's mission and aligning actions with its core values. They create a shared sense of purpose, fostering a collaborative and innovative work environment. This approach increases drive and employee retention and encourages others to follow suit. Mission-driven leaders inspire others by demonstrating behaviors that align with the organization's values (Bourne, 2024). They prioritize transparency, celebrate achievements, foster a sense of belonging, encourage continuous personal and professional development, and are resilient and adaptable. Their focus on long-term goals inspires confidence and dedication within their teams, ensuring the organization's success (McCollum & Kjas, 2007)

Proposition 2: Leaders who effectively communicate the organization's mission and vision inspire and motivate employees, resulting in higher engagement and productivity. When mission-driven leaders convey the mission, they help employees understand the broader significance of their work and how it contributes to achieving organizational goals. This clarity fosters a shared commitment among team members, aligning their efforts toward common objectives. When leaders effectively communicate the organization's purpose, they inspire employees to engage more deeply with their roles and collaborate with others (Axiom 2). This inspiration cultivates a positive climate where creativity and innovation thrive, as employees feel motivated to contribute ideas that support the mission. In essence, this highlights the role of communication in leadership effectiveness, emphasizing how mission-driven leaders' clear and inspiring communication of purpose contributes to creating a positive, innovative, and collaborative organizational climate.

Axiom 3: Mission-driven leaders are strategically focused. Mission-driven leaders focus on strategic planning and decision-making that aligns with the organization's mission, creating a cohesive and motivated workforce (Ruben & Gigliotti, 2021). They set clear, achievable goals that drive performance and innovation, navigate challenges, seize opportunities, and ensure sustained progress toward long-term objectives. This approach enhances organizational efficiency, strengthens employee engagement, and helps in resource allocation. Mission-driven leaders provide stability and direction, ensuring the organization remains resilient and adaptable (Wang et al., 2016). Their unwavering commitment to the mission drives success and fulfills the organization's fundamental purpose.

Proposition 3: Mission-oriented leaders drive accountability, performance excellence, and competitive advantage. Mission-driven leaders are defined by their dedication to achieving the organization's mission and goals. By maintaining a strategic focus on these mission-related objectives, leaders set clear expectations and priorities for the organization (Axiom 2). This focus on alignment ensures that every decision and action is oriented towards advancing the mission and enhancing team members' accountability. When leaders prioritize mission-related goals, they promote a culture of performance excellence where individuals and teams strive to exceed expectations. Employees are motivated to deliver high-quality work that contributes directly to achieving strategic outcomes, thereby enhancing organizational effectiveness (Axiom 4). This emphasis on excellence improves operational efficiency and strengthens the organization's competitive advantage in the marketplace.

Moreover, maintaining a strategic focus on mission-related goals enables leaders to allocate resources effectively and optimize organizational capabilities. Leaders foster collaboration and alignment across departments by guiding efforts toward a unified purpose, further enhancing productivity and innovation (Axiom 3). This unified approach drives short-term success and positions the organization for sustainable growth and long-term viability.

Axiom 4: Mission-driven leadership is adaptive to change. Mission-driven leaders are adaptable, aligning their strategies with the organization's mission and responding to the evolving environments (Northouse, 2021). They foster a culture of innovation and continuous improvement, ensuring organizational resilience. They prioritize learning and

development, leveraging stakeholder feedback, and emphasize ethical decision-making. Moreover, McCombs and Williams (2021) opined that school leaders' adaptability is a significant driver of organizational resilience, guiding organizations through periods of change and ensuring sustained success in a rapidly changing world.

Proposition 4: Leaders who exhibit adaptability and flexibility in response to changing environments and challenges foster organizational resilience and sustain competitive advantage. Mission-driven leaders understand the importance of continuous learning and improvement in adapting to changing environments and achieving long-term organizational goals. By prioritizing ongoing development and adaptation of strategies, these leaders ensure that the organization remains agile and responsive to external challenges and opportunities. Continuous learning enables leaders to refine their understanding of market dynamics, technological advancements, and stakeholder expectations, essential for making informed strategic decisions. This approach enhances organizational adaptability, allowing leaders to proactively adjust strategies to align with evolving mission-related goals (Axiom 4). Furthermore, leaders who emphasize continuous learning foster a culture of innovation and creativity within the organization. Employees are encouraged to experiment with new ideas and approaches, which can lead to breakthrough innovations that support the organization's mission (Axiom 2). This commitment to learning also enhances employee engagement and retention, as individuals feel supported in their professional development and growth (Axiom 1).

Conclusions

Given the multifaceted nature of the private school heads' work, the researcher developed a theory that would encapsulate their motivations and characteristics, creating a unified framework of dynamic, resilient, and innovative school heads worthy of praise and emulation for their admirable and zealous work. Thus, the theory of Mission-Driven Leadership is developed.

Mission-Driven Leadership Theory posits that a mission-driven leader is *aligned with the organization's core values, inspires and motivates, is strategically focused, and is adaptive to change*. The convergence of the two premium qualities of Mission-Driven Leadership – Alignment and Focus, and Inspiration and Adaptability create a robust framework that promotes organizational cohesion, innovation, and sustained success.

The merging of these elements creates a dynamic organizational culture where clarity of purpose, ethical conduct, strategic alignment, and a commitment to learning blend to drive sustained success. This integrated approach enhances operational efficiency and cultivates a positive work environment where employees feel valued and motivated to contribute their best efforts. Mission-driven leadership is characterized by its holistic approach to aligning organizational goals with ethical principles, fostering engagement through effective communication, and promoting adaptability and continuous improvement to ensure long-term viability and success.

Figure 2. Mission-Driven Leadership Theory Framework

Recommendations (Theory Validation)

Theory validation systematically assesses a theory to ascertain its applicability, correctness, and dependability in practical contexts. Empirical research techniques are needed to collect data and interpret the results, such as surveys, case studies, and longitudinal studies (Yin, 2018). To validate the notion of Mission-Driven Leadership, researchers may utilize longitudinal studies to investigate the enduring impacts of leadership practices on employee engagement and organizational performance. Furthermore, surveys and questionnaires can reveal information about stakeholder perceptions and experiences, and comparison studies can assist in discerning the influence of mission-driven leadership from alternative leadership philosophies. In conducting further studies to validate the theory, the researchers should adhere to ethical principles of respect for autonomy, privacy and confidentiality, beneficence, justice, and professional responsibility.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

By ethical norms, this study did not include the involvement of human participants. The study predominantly concentrated on constructing a theoretical framework, guaranteeing the absence of any need for personal data or human contacts. According to ethical principles, the study did not require authorization from an ethics review board to conduct

research involving human beings. In addition, all relevant research and material used in formulating the axioms and propositions were appropriately cited and referenced, guaranteeing academic honesty and upholding intellectual property rights. Nonetheless, the researcher observed objectivity in analyzing and generating the proposed theory.

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